

Hesitancy and refusal on vaccination among parents

Kim Margaret R. Pielago*, Jan Jacob L. Martizano, Nikka F. Nillas, Michelle Marie Q. Rubia,
Dianne P. Sanchez, Dennis C. Sison
Nursing Department, School of Health Science Professions, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City,
Cavite, Philippines
*Corresponding author

Abstract

Vaccination is very important in a children's life, as this will protect children from serious illness and complications of vaccine preventable disease such as measles, mumps and whooping cough. Some parents have lost their faith and were unable to participate in vaccines and immunization services as a result of argument-inducing incidents that they learn about from various outlets, such as the press. The purpose of the study is to determine the life experiences among mothers of an unimmunized child to address how they view their hesitancy in immunization. The study also provides valuable insight into factors that affect the reasons for defaulting from immunization programs. Descriptive survey design was used to identify parents who were hesitant about the vaccination in terms of behavior, safety, efficacy, general attitude and demographic variables. The researchers used a PACV tool to identify hesitant parents who often follow an alternative vaccine schedule. This study includes three sub-domains: Behavioral Domain, Safety/Efficacy Domain, and General Attitudes Domain. With one hundred forty-six (146) respondents who participated in the study, parent-respondents' attitudes toward vaccination are marked by a decrease of hesitancy. Respondents are somewhat concerned that their children will receive more shots than is necessary for their health. The remaining parents who postponed their children's vaccinations and who choose not to have their children vaccinated for reasons other than sickness or allergy based on the findings of the behavioral domain of hesitancy towards vaccination. The delays and non-submission contributed to the hesitancy of parents towards vaccination. This study aims to educate parents about the vaccination and how critical it is to their health, especially that of their children.

Keywords: *Vaccination; Hesitancy; Refusal; Parents; Diseases.*

To cite this article:

Pielago, K. M. R., Martizano, J. J. L., Nillas, N. F., Rubia, M. M. Q., Sanchez, D. P., & Sison, D. C. (2022). Hesitancy and refusal on vaccination among parents. *Faculty Research Journal – Nursing*, 8, 35-44.

Introduction

Being a parent is a significant role that can bring a lot of joy and satisfaction, as well as a lot of challenges. To be a successful parent, you must be willing to always take responsibility while having patience, empathy, and discipline. Nurturing your child and watching them grow and evolve into their own individual will help you develop habits that give your life meaning and purpose. Assuring their children's health and safety, preparing them for adulthood, and imparting cultural values are the three basic objectives that parents have in common. Healthy development depends on a strong parent-child bond (Frosch et al., 2021).

Being a responsible parent entails learning how to shield their children from harm and, more significantly, protecting their children's health by taking the appropriate safety measures, such as making their child vaccinated. The public's autonomy with relation to vaccines is a major concern. It is a critical health measure for prevention of communicable disease. This means that their goal is to protect people from diseases and prevent them from spreading.

The eradication of smallpox, poliomyelitis, and other notable declines in the prevalence of diseases that can be prevented by vaccination are evidence of its efficacy (Rodrigues & Plotkin, 2020). Vaccination is particularly important in a child's life, it will protect children from serious illness and complications of vaccine preventable disease such as measles, mumps, and whooping cough.

Immunizations save two to three million lives annually (Feldstein et al., 2017). Vaccines are essential in preventing avoidable child deaths because they shield kids from dangerous illnesses. Additionally, UNICEF's immunization program assists in identifying children who have been neglected by the health system and can provide these mothers and children with additional life-saving care. More children nowadays are protected by vaccinations, but nearly one in five newborns may not receive the essential shots to be healthy. All other advancements in maternal and child health are at risk due to low immunization rates for vulnerable and underprivileged children. Every year, diseases that can be prevented by vaccination claim the lives of more than 1.5 million youngsters. Vaccinating children in every community, the cold chain, vaccine supply, innovation, and disease eradication and elimination programs are the five ways that UNICEF is able to immunize children who are most in need.

The "Expanded Program on Immunization" in the Philippines aims to guarantee that women and children, especially babies, have access to age-appropriate immunizations to avoid certain diseases. The Expanded Program on Immunization (EPI) was created in 1976 to guarantee that mothers and infants/children have access to routinely advised infant/childhood immunizations (DOH, 2016). The EPI originally covered six diseases that may be prevented by vaccination: measles, pertussis, tetanus, diphtheria, poliomyelitis, and tuberculosis. The risk of infectious disease for both young and old has grown over the past decades due to an increase in the rate of parents refusing vaccinations (Salmon et al., 2015).

Following the Dengvaxia issue, more parents in today's Philippine culture are declining to participate in various immunization programs. In February 2018, only 60% of Filipino children are receiving their regular vaccinations, despite the DOH's yearly immunization rate objective of approximately 85%. These specific figures support the significant decline in Filipino children's vaccination rates in 2018 (DOH, 2019).

The researchers aim to determine parents' resistance to vaccination in terms of behavior, safety/efficacy, and general attitude domains in light of the recent controversy surrounding Dengvaxia and statistics showing a decrease in the number of children who do not receive immunizations on time. The results of the study provided information on the proportion of parents who were hesitant to vaccinate their children. Health centers will also utilize the data to plan and enhance health promotion initiatives to lower the percentage of vaccine defaulters.

Parents' Hesitancy towards Vaccination

Many parents, both globally and locally, have lost faith and are unable to participate in vaccines and immunization services because of argument-inducing incidents that they learn about from various outlets, such as the press. In fact, vaccination is one of the best ways of eliminating and avoiding deadly diseases that previously had no cure.

Dubé and MacDonald (2020) asserted that vaccine uptake is significantly influenced by vaccination services' accessibility and convenience. Additionally, vaccine acceptability may be impacted by the caliber of immunization programs. Future vaccination decisions may be influenced by prior experiences with vaccinations and vaccination services, such as unfavorable interactions with vaccine providers. One of the primary factors influencing a kid's non-vaccination or incomplete vaccination status was feeling under pressure from doctors to vaccinate their child. Another known obstacle to vaccination is fear of needles and post-vaccination soreness. Parents' top concern over vaccinations was their child's discomfort from the injections.

Meanwhile, Arceo et al. (2021) elaborated that most of the mothers believed that immunization could prevent vaccine-preventable illnesses. Increasing parity, education beyond high school, increased vaccination knowledge, and use of free vaccines at the health center were found to be some sociodemographic characteristics that encourage parents to finish their child's vaccinations. However, poor vaccine supply, migration from another barangay, misplaced immunization cards, and a history of post-vaccination illness were the obstacles to completing the immunization.

Similarly, Diekema and the Committee on Bioethics (2016) explained that a number of factors, such as the likelihood of contracting the disease if unimmunized and the morbidity and mortality associated with infection, will determine whether parents put their children at significant risk of serious harm by refusing immunization. According to Keane et al. (2016), they have identified four parent profiles: the "vaccine believer" parents, who were persuaded of the advantages of vaccination; the "cautious" parents, who were emotionally invested in their child and found it difficult to watch them get vaccinated; the "relaxed" parents, who exhibited some skepticism regarding vaccines; and the "unconvinced" parents, who mistrusted vaccinations and vaccination policy. Furthermore, up to 40% of American parents delay or refuse some vaccinations for their kids due to worries about vaccine safety in an effort to prevent uncommon reactions. Immunization delays may also result from obstacles to healthcare access. However, postponing certain vaccinations can also raise the risk of fever-related seizures in addition to keeping kids vulnerable against illness for longer. Vaccines given during this time may raise the risk of fever and, consequently, febrile seizures because they stimulate the immune system to produce a stronger defense (Hambridge, 2016).

In contrast, Rainey et al. (2011) highlighted the various causes of undervaccination and non-vaccination, suggesting that a multifaceted strategy is required to reach children who are undervaccinated and unvaccinated. Improving outreach programs, vaccine availability, and health worker training can help solve immunization system problems; however, undervaccination and non-vaccination related to parental attitudes and knowledge are more challenging to address and probably call for local solutions.

Individual vaccine decision-making is a multifaceted and intricate process. Numerous obstacles to vaccination have been discovered, including fear of adverse effects, lack of a provider's suggestion to get vaccinated, opinions about the effectiveness and utility of vaccines, mistrust of the motivations behind them, and ignorance of the necessity of getting vaccinated. Without considering the "processes and pathways" that lead to vaccination rejection or the larger sociocultural context in which these barriers are anchored, these obstacles are frequently presented as distinct and quantifiable factors (Nichter, 1995). Vaccine uptake is significantly influenced by the accessibility and convenience of the immunization services (Briss et al., 2002). Furthermore, vaccine acceptability may be influenced by the finest immunization services. Decisions about vaccination might be influenced by prior research on vaccines and vaccination options, as well as negative experiences with vaccine providers.

Busse et al. (2011) found that fear of needles and pain following vaccination are other known obstacles to vaccination. Vaccines are one of the most crucial components of pediatric preventative care (McClure et al., 2017). However, vaccination rates have dropped to dangerously low levels in some communities due to parents' growing doubts about the necessity and safety of vaccines. Vaccine reluctance has far-reaching consequences. Higher levels of burnout and poorer levels of job satisfaction are reported by community doctors who frequently deal with parents who are apprehensive about vaccinations. Unsurprisingly, vaccine hesitancy has also had a direct impact on immunization rates, which are associated with higher rates of morbidity, mortality, and usage of emergency rooms.

According to McLaughlin (2019), a two-year-old, politically charged scandal involving a government-led dengue vaccination software has been a driving force behind the outbreak, in line with some doctors, medical examiners, and government officials in the Philippines. This scandal has cratered an already unsteady confidence in vaccines. Many parents stopped going to vaccination clinics and started refusing medical examiners who offered at-home immunizations, while it is yet unknown if the software caused any deaths.

The dissemination of false information and myths regarding vaccines was aided by social media. The anti-vaccine frenzy in the Philippines began in April 2016 when the previous government published a program to provide a mass vaccination for dengue, a tropical mosquito-borne illness. Parents whose children had received vaccinations were concerned by the announcement, and some politicians and the media connected the vaccine to deaths with very little proof.

In a study by Benin et al. (2006), the concept of risk is frequently closely associated with concepts of agreement with authorities, health practitioners, or public fitness facilities, as well as the interactions between those actors. In a qualitative longitudinal study, Benin et al. discovered that new moms' decisions on vaccinating their infants were heavily influenced by their level of trust. Because moms believed that "diseases are not around" or "no longer so bad" and that they had little to celebrate with VPD, the investigators concluded that the reliance on trust was particularly impressive.

Null Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant difference between the parent's behavior, safety, efficacy, general attitudes domains and the demographic data towards vaccination.

Methodology

Research Design

The method that was utilized is a descriptive survey study design. In this study, quantitative research was done to identify parents who are hesitant about vaccination, data were collected and analyzed in terms of behavior, safety, efficacy, general attitude, and demographic variables. Descriptive studies aim to observe, characterize, and record aspects as they naturally occur (Polit & Beck, 2021). In this study, the researchers used descriptive design to describe the parent's hesitancy towards vaccination in terms of behavioral, safety/efficacy, and general attitude domain. Moreover, comparative design was used to identify the significant difference of parents' hesitancy towards vaccination in terms of behavioral, safety/efficacy, general attitude domain when grouped according to age, gender, marital status, relation to child, number of children, and highest educational attainment.

Parents were chosen as the participants in this study. When it comes to vaccinations for their children, it is the parents on whom must place a greater emphasis. This study explored how to determine how many parents are worried about the vaccine so that the researcher can help them understand the benefits of the vaccine for their children. As a data collection tool, the researchers used a web-based survey via Google Survey Form. This way, they will learn more about what parents think about vaccines and how much they know about vaccinations. With the input of the respondents, the researchers were able to determine if they are still hesitant about the vaccine. In this way, the presented parents with more knowledge about the vaccine's benefits, making it easier for health workers to obtain parents' trust.

Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling, which is based on the idea that researchers' knowledge of the population can be used to choose sample members, was applied in this study (Polit & Beck, 2021). The researchers made the deliberate decision to include as many different types of respondents as feasible, or they may choose participants who are thought to be representative of the population in question or very informed about the topic being studied. Purposive sampling is the best method to use for this research because of the ability to freely choose the population or the respondents who are able to fit in with the criteria.

Instrumentation

A popular method for identifying vaccine-hesitant parents who frequently adhere to a different vaccination schedule is Parents Attitude about Childhood Vaccine (PACV) (Opel et al., 2011). The study utilized a questionnaire which consisted of demographic profile of the respondents, PACV survey within behavioral domain, safety/efficacy domain, and general attitude domain. This survey will identify parents who are hesitant towards vaccination. They were ordered in three sub domains with their respective item numbers: Behavioral domain (1-4), Safety/Efficacy (5-10), and General attitude (11-15). A score of 15 and above are considered hesitant.

The researchers provided a survey through Google Form which indicates a consent form for the respondents to know what the survey is. The demographic form and PACV tool were used, explained, and completed by the participants. After the survey, the researchers collected all the data and the parents who scored more than 15 were considered hesitant. In the study, the data collection methods and statistical weighing were used to enable these findings to be applied to the population of Cavite. This study also shows that parent-respondents are worried that the vaccine is not safe to be given for their children. Overall, the respondent's attitude towards vaccines was marked as not hesitant. The researchers also concluded the remaining parents who did not continue their child's vaccination and who chose not to receive based on the findings of the behavioral domain towards vaccination. The study also shows that parents are the main decision makers when it comes to their children's health, whereas the researchers want this to make it easier for the respondents.

Ethical Consideration

The study's validity will be guaranteed and its contribution to scientific research will be encouraged by adhering to ethical criteria. (1) Research participants' privacy must be protected; (2) Participants must never feel coerced into taking part in a study; (3) There must be a trusting relationship between the researcher and the participants; (4) Participants must not be harmed in any way; and (5) Participants' and organizations' anonymity must be protected; and (6) Only evaluate relevant factors that are essential to the effort or program being carried out.

Data Analysis

This study aims to determine the parent's hesitancy towards vaccination in terms of behavior, safety/efficacy, and general attitude domains. To do so, certain mathematical tools were relied on to ascertain the same; thus:

1. To determine the demographic data of the parents, frequency and distribution was employed.
2. To determine the significant difference between the parent's behavior, safety, efficacy, general attitudes domains and the demographic data towards vaccination, Kruskal-Wallis will be used to analyze the differences among group means in a sample. P-value was used to determine whether there is a significant difference between the means of two groups.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the parents. 146 people with a range of demographic traits participated in the study. The majority of respondents were between the ages of 42 and 47 (23.97%), followed by those between the ages of 24 and 29 (17.12%) and 48 and 53 (17.12%). The majority of the respondents (77.40%) were female, while 22.60% were male. The majority of respondents (60.96%) were married, with single people coming in second (25.34%). In terms of family composition, the majority (58.90%) had one to two children, whereas only a small percentage reported no children or bigger families with more than five children.

Table 1. Profile Characteristics of the Participants (n=146)

Profile	Measure	n	%
Age	18 to 23 years old	15	10.27
	24 to 29 years old	25	17.12
	30 to 35 years old	13	8.90
	36 to 41 years old	14	9.59
	42 to 47 years old	35	23.97
	48 to 53 years old	25	17.12
	54 to 59 years old	15	10.27
Gender	60 to 65 years old	4	2.74
	Female	113	77.40
Marital Status	Male	33	22.60
	Live-in Partner	11	7.53
	Married	89	60.96
	Separated	6	4.11
	Single	37	25.34
Number of Children	Widowed	3	2.05
	None	10	6.85
	1 to 2	86	58.90
	3 to 4	43	29.45
	5 to 6	3	2.05
	7 to 8	3	2.05
Educational Attainment	9 to 10	1	0.68
	Elementary Graduate	5	3.42
	High School Graduate	37	25.34
	College Undergraduate	5	3.42
	College Graduate	79	54.11
Number of Family Members	Postgraduate	2	1.37
	Vocational Course	18	12.33
	2	7	4.79
	3	31	21.23
	4	34	23.29
	5	32	21.92
Religious Affiliation	More than 5	42	28.77
	Catholic	114	78.08
	Christian	27	18.49
	Iglesia Ni Cristo	3	2.05
Source of Information about Vaccination	Others	2	1.37
	TV, Radio, Newspaper, and Internet	51	34.93
	Local People	6	4.11
	Government Hospital	8	5.48
	Private Hospital	24	16.44
	Health Centers	54	36.99
	None	3	2.05

In terms of educational attainment, 25.34% of participants had only completed high school, while more than half (54.11%) had completed college. Postgraduate studies (1.37%), elementary education (3.42%), and vocational courses (12.33%) were completed by smaller percentages. The largest group of respondents reported households with more than five members (28.77%), closely followed by families with four members (23.29%) and five members (21.92%). These results imply that the majority of respondents came from homes that were modestly sized and had comparatively high levels of education.

In terms of religion, the majority of respondents (78.08%) identified as Catholic, followed by Christians (18.49%), with just a small percentage belonging to Iglesia ni Cristo or other affiliations. Health clinics were the most popular source of information on vaccinations (36.99%), followed by radio, television, newspapers, and the internet (34.93%). While few participants relied on locals, government hospitals, or reported having no source of vaccination information, private hospitals were also a substantial source of information (16.44%).

Table 2. Persons who take care of the child when he/she is not with the parents or at school

Person	Everyday	Sometimes a week	Once a week	Sometimes a month	Sometimes a year	Total	Rank
Grandparents	38	11	6	12	18	85	1
Brothers or sisters (adults)	20	10	1	9	6	46	3
Non-remunerated friends, neighbor, other persons	2	1	0	2	0	5	5
Remunerated persons	10	4	0	2	2	18	4
I do the childcare all by myself	29	5	1	6	19	60	2

Table 2 reveals the persons who take care of the child when he/she is not with the parents or at school. With the highest overall frequency of 85 and the top ranking, this table demonstrates that grandparents are the children’s primary caretakers when they are not with their parents or at school. This also suggests that grandparents are an important source of regular childcare assistance. With a total frequency of 60, parents who handle childcare alone were the second most frequent response, indicating that many parents still bear personal responsibility for their children’s upbringing. With 46 responses, adult siblings came in third, while remunerated individuals like paid caregivers came in fourth with 18. With only five responses, non-remunerated friends, neighbors, or other people were the least trusted caretakers, ranking fifth. The results indicate that close family members, particularly grandparents, provide the majority of childcare support, as opposed to hired caregivers or non-family members.

Table 3. Parents’ Hesitancy towards Vaccination in terms of Behavioral Domain

Behavioral Domain	Kruskal-Wallis	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
Age	2.033	0.566	Accept Null Hypothesis	No Significant Difference
Gender	4.332	0.037	Reject Null Hypothesis	Significant Difference
Marital Status	3.241	0.518	Accept Null Hypothesis	No Significant Difference
Number of Children	8.568	0.128	Accept Null Hypothesis	No Significant Difference

Table 3 shows the testing of significant differences in the parents’ hesitation to vaccinate. The researchers have decided to reject the null hypothesis because the gender p-value (0.037) is smaller than the significance level of 0.05. As a result, parental refusal to vaccinate their children varies significantly depending on their gender. However, there is no discernible difference in the parents’ hesitation to vaccinate their children based on their age, marital status, or number of children.

Table 4. Parents’ Hesitancy towards Vaccination in terms of Safety/Efficacy Domain

Safety/Efficacy Domain	Kruskal-Wallis	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
Age	2.033	0.566	Accept Null Hypothesis	No Significant Difference
Gender	4.332	0.037	Reject Null Hypothesis	Significant Difference
Marital Status	3.241	0.518	Accept Null Hypothesis	No Significant Difference
Number of Children	8.568	0.128	Accept Null Hypothesis	No Significant Difference

Table 4 displays the testing of substantial differences in the parents’ reluctance to vaccinate regarding safety and effectiveness. The researchers have decided to reject the null hypothesis because the p-value for the number of children (0.047) is less than the significance level of 0.05. Consequently, the researchers concluded that there is a significant difference in parents’ reluctance to vaccinate their children due to concerns about safety and effectiveness. However, there is no significant difference in the parents’ reluctance to get vaccinated due to concerns about safety or efficacy based on their gender, age, or marital status.

Table 5. Parents’ Hesitancy towards Vaccination in terms of General Attitudes Domain

General Attitudes	Kruskal-Wallis	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
Age	0.862	0.835	Accept Null Hypothesis	No Significant Difference
Gender	1.052	0.305	Accept Null Hypothesis	No Significant Difference
Marital Status	2.869	0.580	Accept Null Hypothesis	No Significant Difference
Number of Children	4.701	0.453	Accept Null Hypothesis	No Significant Difference

The testing of significant differences in parents’ reluctance to get vaccinated about general attitudes is shown in Table 20. The researchers decided to accept the null hypothesis because the p-values for age (0.835), gender (0.305), marital status (0.580), and number of children (0.453) were all higher than the significance level of 0.05. As a result, the researchers realized that the respondents’ age, gender, marital status, and number of children did not significantly affect the parents’ reluctance to vaccinate.

Conclusion

Every year, vaccination is one aspect of public health that saves millions of lives. Currently, there are numerous outbreaks occurring all over the world. The Philippines is no exception, with polio and measles outbreaks resurfacing. It is concluded that the primary concern of parents about vaccination of their children is the safety and efficacy, as there is a substantial difference in parent hesitancy against vaccination in terms of the number of children. The parent-respondents are particularly worried that the vaccine is unsafe for their children, that it may not prevent the disease, and that it may cause severe side effects in their children. In general, parent-respondents’ attitudes toward vaccination are marked by a decrease of hesitancy. Respondents are particularly concerned that their children will receive more shots than is necessary for their health. The researchers concluded that the remaining parents who postponed their children’s vaccinations and who chose not to have their children vaccinated for reasons other than sickness or allergy based on the findings of the behavioral domain of hesitancy towards vaccination. The researchers further concluded that the delays and non-submission for vaccination are brought about by hesitancy of parents towards vaccination. Finally, it is concluded that parents, regardless of their profile, have the same apprehension about vaccination because they are subjected to, more or less, the same information, especially negative information, that they hear and see in the media, which makes them reluctant to send their children for vaccination or to postpone vaccination shots for their children.

Recommendation

A research study should be conducted on how to effectively utilize the internet for vaccination campaigns which includes encouragements to undergo vaccine, health teaching. To develop systems on the internet, they can connect the mother to their specific barangay health center and can answer the mother’s inquiries, set reminders about the schedule of next vaccination, and receive barangay health center announcements and activities. Fact checking and verifying the accuracy of the information conveyed by media and on the internet is crucial in combating vaccine hesitancy. False and inaccurate information that circulates on media and internet must be urgently corrected by health teaching in the health center, thus recommending that health care workers to pro-actively watch out for circulating information about vaccines and ask parents on their worries about the topic. Health workers may also utilize it to spread awareness, to follow up, and to answer parent’s questions. For example, launching online campaigns to educate and encourage parents to let their children receive vaccine and give a specific barangay health center’s operating hour and addresses to help parent’s access the health services.

The study's aim is to educate parents about vaccination and how critical it is to their health, especially that of their children. The researchers will provide them with more information about the vaccine's positive effects on their health and how it can improve and enhance their immune system, resulting in less hesitant parents. We all know that parents are the main decision-makers when it comes to their children's health; in this study, we want to make it easier for them to make the decision without having to think about the vaccine that their children need. We would be better able to stop being infected easily or the spread of disease in the future and fewer people will get sick.

References

- Arceo, E., Dizon, J. C., Chavez, M., Cordero, P. K., de Leon, M. R., de Luna, J., de Vera, T. F., Jose, J., Manalo II, L. D., & Tiongco, R. E. (2021). Knowledge, attitude, and practices of mothers from a rural community in Pampanga, Philippines toward childhood immunization: a cross sectional survey. *Vacunas (English Edition)*, 22(3), 183-188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vacune.2021.10.010>
- Benin, A. L., Wisler-Scher, D. J., Colson, E., Shapiro, E. D., & Holmboe, E. S. (2006). Qualitative analysis of mothers' decision-making about vaccines for infants: the importance of trust. *Pediatrics*, 117(5), 1532-1541. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2005-1728>
- Briss, P., Shefer, A., & Rodewald, L. (2002). Improving vaccine coverage in communities and healthcare systems: No magic bullets. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 23(1), 70-71. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0749-3797\(02\)00438-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0749-3797(02)00438-5)
- Busse, J. W., Walji, R., & Wilson, K. (2011). Parents' experiences discussing pediatric vaccination with healthcare providers: A survey of Canadian naturopathic patients. *PLoS One*, 6(8), e22737. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0022737>
- Diekema, D. S., & Committee on Bioethics. (2005). Responding to parental refusals of immunization of children. *Pediatrics*, 115(5), 1428-1431. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2005-0316>
- Department of Health. (2016). *Situational analysis: Expanded Program on Immunization*. <https://caro.doh.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/Situational-Analysis-EPI-2015-final-1.pdf>
- Department of Health. (2019). *A briefer on the health programs of the Department of Health*. https://caro.doh.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/Program-Briefer_2019-v7.pdf
- Dubé, E., & MacDonald, N. E. (2020). How can a global pandemic affect vaccine hesitancy? *Expert Review of Vaccines*, 19(10), 899-901. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14760584.2020.1825944>
- Feldstein, L. R., Mariat, S., Gacic-Dobo, M., Diallo, M. S., Conklin, L. M., & Wallace, A. S. (2017). Global routine vaccination coverage, 2016. *MMWR: Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, 66(45), 1252-1255. <https://doi.org/10.15585/mmwr.mm6645a3>
- Frosch, C. A., Schoppe-Sullivan, S. J., & O'Banion, D. D. (2021). Parenting and child development: A relational health perspective. *American Journal of Lifestyle Medicine*, 15(1), 45-59. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1559827619849028>
- Keane, M. T., Walter, M. V., Patel, B. I., Moorthy, S., Stevens, R. B., Bradley, K. M., Buford, J. F., Anderson, E. L., Anderson, L. P., Tibbals, K., & Vernon, T. M. (2005). Confidence in vaccination: a parent model. *Vaccine*, 23(19), 2486-2493. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2004.10.026>
- McClure, C. C., Cataldi, J. R., & O'Leary, S. T. (2017). Vaccine hesitancy: where we are and where we are going. *Clinical Therapeutics*, 39(8), 1550-1562. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinthera.2017.07.003>
- McLaughlin, T. (2019, March 22). *Philippine measles outbreak fed by distrust of vaccines – rooted in vaccination scandal*. Los Angeles Times. <https://www.latimes.com/world/la-fg-philippines-measles-20190322-story.html>

- Nichter, M. (1995). Vaccinations in the Third World: a consideration of community demand. *Social Science & Medicine*, 41(5), 617-632. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-9536\(95\)00034-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-9536(95)00034-5)
- Opel, D. J., Mangione-Smith, R., Taylor, J. A., Korfiatis, C., Wiese, C., Catz, S., & Martin, D. P. (2011). Development of a survey to identify vaccine-hesitant parents: the parent attitudes about childhood vaccines survey. *Human Vaccines*, 7(4), 419-425. <https://doi.org/10.4161/hv.7.4.14120>
- Polit, D. F., & Beck, C. T. (2021). *Nursing research: Generating and assessing evidence for nursing practice* (11th ed.). Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- Rainey, J. J., Watkins, M., Ryman, T. K., Sandhu, P., Bo, A., & Banerjee, K. (2011). Reasons related to non-vaccination and under-vaccination of children in low and middle income countries: findings from a systematic review of the published literature, 1999–2009. *Vaccine*, 29(46), 8215-8221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2011.08.096>
- Rodrigues, C., & Plotkin, S. A. (2020). Impact of vaccines; health, economic and social perspectives. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 11, 550510. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.01526>
- Salmon, D. A., Dudley, M. Z., Glanz, J. M., & Omer, S. B. (2015). Vaccine hesitancy: causes, consequences, and a call to action. *Vaccine*, 33, D66-D71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2015.09.035>